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IMMEDIATE RESULTS OF MINI-GASTRIC BYPASS IN THE TRADITIONAL WAY FOR OBESITY AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Relevance of the problem. Obesity is currently becoming a global health problem worldwide, as about 1.7 billion people are overweight [5;6]. According to WHO, about 7% of the world's adult population is obese, while in developed countries about a third of the population (33.3%) is overweight [1]. A direct relationship has been established between the increase in the prevalence of obesity and the growth in cases of type 2 diabetes. According to WHO, the likelihood of developing diabetes increases by 20% with an increase in BMI for every 1 kg/m² [2;3].

In most patients with obesity against the background of type 2 DM, mini-gastrosurgery allows not only to reduce body weight, but also to normalize carbohydrate metabolism starting from the early postoperative period [4]. However, the course of the early postoperative period (in the first 30 days after mini-gastrosurgery) is often overshadowed by the development of postoperative complications, including "adductor loop syndrome". Therefore, the search for ways to solve the problem of obesity against the background of type 2 DM is justified, because it is aimed at improving the results of surgical treatment of obesity against the background of type 2 DM, which was the subject of this study.

The aim of the study is to improve the results of surgical treatment for obesity associated with diabetes mellitus (DM-2) using laparoscopic mini-gastric bypass surgery.

Material and methods of the study. The work is based on the results of a retrospective and prospective analysis of patients with obesity associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus (hereinafter referred to as DM-2) for the period 2023 to 2024 subject to surgical treatment in the private clinic "Sekhat" in Andijan and in the third surgical department of the Clinic of the Andijan State Medical Institute.

The subject of this study was 177 patients with obesity associated with type 2 diabetes. According to the purpose and objectives, the patients under study were conditionally divided into two groups:

- comparison group - (2023) - 49 (27.7%) patients who underwent a retrospective analysis of the results of surgical treatment in compliance with traditional approaches;

- main group - (2024) - 128 (72.3%) patients who underwent a prospective study of the results of surgical treatment using optimized surgical tactics.

The standard of examination of the studied patients before bariatric intervention consisted of an assessment of physical parameters with the implementation of laboratory, instrumental and statistical research methods in accordance with the latest clinical guidelines (Dedov I.I. et al., 2018 and protocols approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Results and discussion. All postoperative complications are conditionally divided into:

- 1) complications directly related to the bariatric surgery (specific complications) - anastomotic suture failure, afferent loop syndrome, hypoglycemic syndrome, diarrhea, gastroesophageal reflux;

- 2) wound - infiltrate, suppuration of the postoperative wound, ligature fistula;

- 3) complications not related to the bariatric surgery, which may also occur in other surgeries (general complications).

In the comparison group, after laparoscopic mini-gastroshunting surgery performed by the traditional method, complications associated with bariatric surgery were noted in 9 (18.4%) patients. Of these, with the first degree of obesity against the background of type 2 DM - in 4 (8.2%) cases, with the second - in 3 (6.1%) and with the third - in 2 (4.1%) cases.

In the comparison group, after laparoscopic mini-gastroshunting surgery performed by the traditional method, wound complications (purulent-septic) were noted in 6 (12.2%) patients. Of these, with the first degree of obesity against the background of type 2 DM - in 1 (2.0%) cases, with the second - in 2 (4.1%) and with the third - in 3 (6.1%) cases.

In the comparison group, after laparoscopic mini-gastroshunting surgery performed in the traditional way, general complications were noted in 5 (10.2%) patients. Of these, with the first degree of obesity against the background of type 2 DM - in 1 (2.0%) cases, with the second - in 2 (4.1%) and with the third - in 2 (4.1%), with a fatal outcome in 1 (2.0%) case.

Summary. The analysis conducted in the comparison group showed that after performing laparoscopic mini-gastroshunting surgery in the traditional way, out of 9 (18.4%) complications directly related to the bariatric surgery, in 7 (14.3%) cases the cause was the development of afferent loop syndrome. This circumstance prompted us to conduct a detailed analysis and develop a preventive measure.

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